

TECHNOLOGY FOR IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS FOR TEACHING SCIENCES

Inoyatova Zulfiya Khamdamovna

Senior teacher of the Department of Primary Education Pedagogy of the Faculty
of Primary Education of TSPU named after Nizami.

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Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the methodological basis of planning the science and processes of education in primary education.

Key words: Primary education, methodology, education, plan, goal setting, methodology.

Introduction.

Today, one of the ways that the pedagogical skills of pedagogues have a significant effect on the increase of their qualifications, pedagogical abilities, and pedagogical competence is to improve the qualifications of continuous professional education. Today, intense discussions are taking place in the scientific-pedagogical community about the nature and structure of professional-pedagogical competence. Goal setting is the teacher's activity on forming the goals and tasks of education and designing ways to achieve them. This is the driving force of the organization of the educational process, which ensures the importance of the educational goal for all participants of the process. Structurally, the goal setting process includes:

Educational goals are a multi-level phenomenon. At one level, the goals of education are general value aspirations that express the social, life, pedagogical ideals of the teacher, pedagogic teacher, society. At another level, the goals of this teacher's activity include not only ideas about the desired changes in schoolchildren as a result of pedagogical actions (effective goals), but also the desired qualities of the educational process itself (procedural goals). as more specific aspirations received.

There is no learning without purpose, because the important features of this process are purposeful. A primary school teacher should keep this in mind and pay more attention to goal setting. Three main goals are distinguished in the theory and practice of education. In the course of the purposeful activity of a primary school teacher, each of these goals has a specific content due to the pedagogical beliefs of the teacher, the goals and value orientations of the educational institution, the characteristics of the student body and the specific characteristics of its living conditions. filled with

Most elementary school teachers choose to educate a well-rounded and well-rounded person as an ideal goal. When choosing an effective goal, class leaders, as a rule, rely on the image (model) developed at the level of the entire educational institution and make the necessary adjustments that reflect the characteristics of the class composition.

Procedural goals are inextricably linked with effective goals, because they provide changes in the educational process, which ensure that students achieve the desired image of a graduate (student). When developing an effective goal, it is necessary to comply with the requirements for the goal instructions of educational activities. They should be:

- aimed at developing the child's personality, forming his intellectual, moral, communicative features; aesthetic and physical potential, students' perception of the surrounding world, practical skills and abilities, methods of creative activity, methods of self-knowledge and self-development, value to oneself and the surrounding social and natural reality mastering a comprehensive system of knowledge about relations;
- related to the interests and values of the members of the class community, taking into account the social order of the state and society, corresponding to the characteristics of the class community and its living conditions;
- provided with necessary resources for their implementation;
- clearly expressed;
- difficult, but really achievable;
- flexible, i.e. capable of adjustment;
- diagnosis.

In the most general form, the plan is a document that shows meaningful directions of activity, determines its order, size, and time limits. Planning functions: guidance, prediction, coordination, control, reproductive. There are different plans: work plan for the year, half year, quarter, month, week, day; work plan for one of the educational areas; a plan to work with a creative or public association; prospective, calendar and current plan of educational work; a plan to prepare and conduct a specific event or work. Sections of the plan, as a rule, reflect the main activities of elementary school students.

Planning is the process of joint activities of the class teacher and students to determine the content and methods of organizing the educational process and life in the class team, the organizers and participants of the planned work, and the deadlines for their implementation. General planning algorithm: goal setting, time determination, choice of plan form, structure (separation of activity

directions and types), team planning, selection of educational tools and forms, distribution of events over time, and planning.

According to M. A. Besova, it is possible to distinguish different ways of involving students in planning: offering to choose one of the forms proposed by the teacher; discuss what children want to do in a class meeting in small groups; organize a competition for the best proposal, an auction of ideas and more.

CONCLUSION

Thus, based on the study and analysis of scientific sources, it is possible to come to the following conclusions: methodological competence, which provides the ability to recognize and solve methodological problems of the educational process of primary education teachers during their pedagogical activity, professional competence the main component and comments on the planning of the lesson process were scientifically analyzed. In order to develop their own methodological knowledge, future elementary school teachers will achieve methodological competence by studying the mentioned tasks and using them in practical experience.

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